

THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL PLATFORMS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE THINKING IN HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the impact of digital educational platforms (DEP) on the development of creative thinking (CrT) in high school students. It analyzes the role of digital technologies in the educational process and their potential to stimulate students' creative engagement. Theoretical approaches to CrT development, such as constructivism, problem-based learning, and gamified learning, are explored, demonstrating their integration within the digital environment. Special attention is given to modern models of digital technology implementation, including SAMR (Substitution, Augmentation, Modification, Redefinition) and TPACK (Technology, Pedagogy, and Content Knowledge), which enable more effective integration of platforms into the learning process. The article provides examples of DEP usage in the USA and Kyrgyzstan, showcasing a positive influence on student engagement and creativity.

Keywords: digital educational platforms (DEP), creative thinking (CrT), high school students, interactive learning, problem-based learning, gamification, flexible learning.

Introduction

The education system is greatly influenced by the digitalization of society, changing traditional teaching approaches and opening up new possibilities for student growth. An important part of these changes is the use of digital education platforms (DEP), which are increasingly being introduced into the learning process in high schools. They provide a variety of resources for engaging and personalized learning, which is essential in today's rapidly changing world focused on digital technology and information. Creative thinking (CrT) is essential in high school education as it allows students to adapt to a constantly evolving world and develop innovative ideas that foster social and technological advancement.

This study is important because educational systems need to be updated to the digital age, as older teaching methods are no longer effective in preparing students for modern challenges. The objective of this research is to analyze how DEP affect the growth of CrT in high school students.

Main part. CrT, its role in the educational process

The ability to generate new and original ideas, non-standard solutions and apply knowledge in new contexts is called CrT. It includes essential components such as divergent thinking (the ability to identify diverse solutions), convergent thinking (the ability to choose optimal solutions), flexibility, and openness to new ideas. This skill is considered crucial in education, especially in high school, where students prepare for professional activities and higher education. Developing this skill supports not only academic success but also personal growth, adaptability, and effective interaction with the world around them.

Modern approaches to developing CrT in an educational setting include various methods aimed at actively engaging students and creating opportunities for self-directed learning. **Constructivism**, for instance, assumes that knowledge is created by students through active engagement with their surroundings. Constructivist methods, such as project-based activities, group work, and research assignments, promote CrT by encouraging student autonomy and engagement. **Problem-based learning** focuses on solving real-world issues that require analysis, research, and the generation of original solutions. This approach fosters critical and CrT, as students encounter problems requiring new ideas and flexible thinking. **Gamified learning**, in turn, incorporates game elements into the learning process, stimulating creativity and enhancing student motivation. Game-based approaches provide a safe space for experimentation and unconventional thinking, which is essential for developing creative skills.

Thus, CrT is a crucial component of the educational process, helping high school students prepare for future professional and academic pursuits. Modern pedagogical approaches create optimal conditions for the development of this skill, allowing students to actively explore and interact with their environment.

Digital educational platforms in the context of modern education

An integral part of today's educational system is DEP. They not only enhance education accessibility but also enable the use of innovative teaching methods aimed at developing critical and CrT skills. These technologies serve as tools and systems utilized to organize the learning process, provide educational resources, and facilitate interaction between students and teachers (table 1).

Types and features of DEP [1, 2]

Type of DEP	Examples of platforms	Features
Online courses and massive open online courses (MOOC)	Coursera, edX, Khan Academy	They provide a wide range of courses with the opportunity to study at your own pace, support the personalization of learning and self-organization.
Learning management systems	Moodle, Google Classroom	It helps to organize educational process management, interaction, knowledge assessment, as well as create a flexible learning environment using digital resources.
Virtual classrooms and interactive learning programs	Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Labster	They allow you to conduct real-time classes, simulations and experiments; promote active learning and CT.
Gamified and project-based educational platforms	Scratch, the educational edition of Minecraft	They develop creativity and project thinking through programming, modeling and project development.
Specialized platforms for specific disciplines	Khan Academy (mathematics), Duolingo (languages)	They provide specialized resources and courses for in-depth study of specific disciplines.

According to the author, DEP encompass a wide range of opportunities and areas. They allow the learning process to be tailored to individual student needs, making education more flexible and accessible. Through such platforms, students can study both general and specialized subjects, utilizing interactive and gamified approaches that stimulate creativity and develop project-thinking skills. Overall, these platforms

transform traditional teaching methods, making them more dynamic and focused on personal development.

The integration of DEP into the educational process requires applying pedagogical models and approaches to maximize their potential. Figure 1 shows the most well-known and widely used models – SAMR (Substitution, Augmentation, Modification, Redefinition) and TPACK (Technology, Pedagogy, and Content Knowledge).

Figure 1. Models of technology integration in education

The **SAMR model**, developed by Ruben Puentedura, describes different levels of technology integration in education, starting from the basic replacement of traditional tools and progressing to a full transformation of the educational process. This model suggests a phased approach to technology implementation, where its use gradually becomes more complex and in-depth. At the first stage, technology is used for simple substitution of traditional methods, such as transitioning from paper textbooks to electronic ones. The next level, augmentation, improves the functionality of educational materials, for instance, by adding interactive elements [3]. At the levels of modification and redefinition, technology begins to radically change the educational process, creating new forms of learning activities, such as virtual labs or cross-cultural projects, that would be impossible without digital tools. Thus,

SAMR emphasizes that technology should not simply reproduce traditional approaches but also offer new forms of interaction and learning that promote CrT development.

The **TPACK model** emphasizes a comprehensive approach to technology use by integrating it with pedagogical expertise and subject content. This model assumes that effective technology integration requires a combination of three core knowledge areas: pedagogical, content, and technological knowledge. Pedagogical knowledge includes understanding effective teaching methods and strategies, while content knowledge involves a deep mastery of the subject. Technological knowledge pertains to the use of digital tools to achieve learning objectives. TPACK helps to understand how best to combine these elements so that DEP not only

complement but also enhance the learning process, enabling students to better comprehend material and develop creative skills.

Thus, both models highlight the importance of a thoughtful approach to integrating digital technologies into education. They help structure and systematize technology use in a way that promotes active learning, stimulating students' creativity and critical thinking.

The impact of DEP on CrT development

Using DEP stimulates CrT as they create an **interactive and flexible learning** environment in which students can learn at their own pace, adapting the process to their individual needs. Platforms provide access to a wide **range of multimedia resources**, such as videos, simulations, interactive tasks, and gamified elements, allowing students to engage more actively and deeply with learning material. For example, interactive simulations and labs enable students to conduct experiments independently and explore different scenarios, fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Virtual environments generally have fewer resource constraints than traditional classrooms, giving students more opportunities for creative experiments and project development. Simulators and interactive labs allow students to conduct virtual experiments in conditions that may be inaccessible in a real classroom, thereby enhancing their research skills and ability to find unconventional solutions.

One example of DEP use is **Minecraft Education Edition**, employed in educational institutions in the USA to develop creative abilities and project-thinking skills. Within educational projects, students can create virtual architectural structures, simulate historical events, or design eco-friendly cities. Such tasks require students to adopt a creative approach, analyze information, and apply knowledge in practice, which fosters the development of their creative abilities and critical thinking [4].

Another example is the **Duolingo** platform, used for learning foreign languages in high school. It supports students through gamified tasks, interactive quizzes, and assignments that require using the language in practical situations. This approach helps students develop creativity and communication skills, utilizing the language to solve problems and perform practical tasks [5].

In Kyrgyzstan, the **Online Mektep** platform has been widely used to ensure access to school education during the pandemic. This platform provides students with remote learning opportunities through interactive lessons, videos, assignments, and quizzes. Incorporating this platform into the educational process enables students to study at a convenient pace, promoting self-organization and independent problem-solving skills, essential components of CrT [6].

These practical examples of DEP usage vividly demonstrate their potential to develop CrT through interactive methodologies and project-based learning. It is also worth noting that studies conducted in the USA and Kyrgyzstan confirm this effect, showing how digital tools are successfully integrated into the educational process.

For instance, in the USA, a study was conducted using the **Scratch** platform to teach programming and digital creativity. More than 200 high school students participated in this study over an academic year, creating their own projects: interactive games, animations, and multimedia stories. The results indicated that students actively using Scratch showed significant improvement in divergent thinking skills and the ability to find unconventional solutions [7]. The platform encouraged students to develop unique projects, requiring them to generate new ideas, design algorithms, and take a creative approach to programming. Researchers noted that students working with Scratch became more confident in their abilities and eagerly shared ideas with classmates, which further enhanced their engagement and developed CrT.

In Kyrgyzstan, the **Taalim-Forum Foundation** conducted a study under the KIX project to implement DEP to improve education quality and develop CrT in high school students. The research, conducted in schools in Bishkek, involved using online platforms and interactive tools to engage students in the educational process. During the experiment, students worked with virtual labs and simulators, allowing them to solve scientific problems and develop project-thinking skills. The results showed that students actively using digital tools demonstrated improved CrT skills and increased motivation to learn [8].

These examples demonstrate that DEP have the potential to develop CrT in high school students. Proper integration of DEP into the educational process helps improve academic performance, increase student engagement, and enhance their ability to solve problems in non-standard ways.

Recommendations for DEP implementation

To successfully select and implement DEP aimed at developing CrT in high school students, teachers need to integrate project-based and problem-oriented activities into the educational process. Examples of real tasks and projects requiring solution development help stimulate CrT, allowing students to explore and present ideas using digital tools. The inclusion of gamified elements, such as points, rewards, and achievement levels, also helps boost student motivation and engagement. Platforms that have successfully applied such methods demonstrate that gamification can actively support learning interest and enhance interaction.

Regular feedback and teacher support play a significant role in creating an environment where students can develop and refine their ideas. Continuous interaction helps students feel more confident while experimenting and expressing themselves. It is also essential to create opportunities for collaborative learning by organizing group projects and virtual classes where students can exchange ideas and work together on tasks. Digital platforms that support real-time collaboration encourage experience sharing and stimulate innovative thinking.

Teaching students' skills in using digital tools, such as programming and working with interactive simulations, helps them better harness platform capabilities and develop CrT. These skills enable them to

effectively use resources for creating digital content, making the learning process richer and more creative.

All these aspects underscore the importance of digital technologies and their integration into the educational process. Platforms that support project-based, interactive, and collaborative learning create an environment that fosters high school students' creativity and innovative thinking.

Conclusion

The introduction of DEP significantly affects the development of computer literacy among high school students, providing new opportunities for interactive, flexible and personalized learning. Through these platforms, students can actively participate in the educational process, design projects, experiment, and find unconventional solutions, which stimulates their creativity and develops critical thinking skills. Effective implementation and use of digital platforms should include teacher support, course adaptation to individual student needs, and the creation of opportunities for collaboration and teamwork.

The use of DEP offers ample opportunities for the development of creative abilities and independence of students. Integrating these technologies is an essential part of the modern educational environment and requires efforts from schools, teachers, and students to achieve high results in developing creative and critical thinking.

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